

CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING IN THE PROCESS OF STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article discusses the subject-language integrated approach (CLIL), its features in teaching a foreign language. Currently, this approach is characterized in the world scientific and methodological literature as an innovative approach to the organization of bilingual education and has two goals: the implementation of education in two subject areas - language and subject; various interpretations of its essence are presented, its varieties, possibilities and features of implementation in bilingual education are distinguished through the application of its basic principles and strategies.

Keywords: Content and language integrated learning, CLIL principles, stages of CLIL implementation, foreign language teaching.

Modern complex and constantly changing living conditions dictate higher demands on human capabilities, both physical and social. The comprehensive development of the individual is the paramount task of education today. That is why the most important learning objectives are the development and formation of a strong and reliable system of knowledge, skills and abilities that are necessary for the future independent activity of students.

Knowledge of a foreign language, especially English, is becoming a basic skill in modern conditions; it is an absolute necessity for a successful career and personal growth. One of the reasons for this global trend is clearly reflected in the extremely important observation of the British linguist D. Greddall, who claims that these educational and social changes are caused by the development of the Internet and the parallel growth of globalization [7].

Thus, the popularity of bilingual education is increasing every day, and this situation, of course, requires changes in the teaching of a foreign language, that is, it is necessary to develop new effective approaches and methods, forms and ways of organizing the process of language acquisition. To this end, in 2004, the European Commission recommended a subject-language integrated approach (CLIL - content and language integrated learning) for implementation on the scale of universal education. The principle of operation of this approach is bilingual, namely: the subject is studied through a foreign language, and at the same time a foreign language is studied through the subject. It is important to note that this approach does not require the addition of additional academic hours to the curriculum [9].

Moreover, within the framework of Kazakh education, the subject-language integrated approach could be considered as one of the ways to solve the problems of small rural schools, in which the academic workload of the teacher often exceeds the norm. To date, there are quite a large number of definitions of the subject-language integrated approach (CLIL), each of which, to

one degree or another, characterizes its multifaceted essence.

For example, F. Ball, who works within the framework of this approach in Spain, gives five definitions in his article [4]. The first and most simplified is interpreted by the European Commission as follows: "Subject-language integrated is education in which students learn a subject through a foreign language and vice versa" [9, p. 8-9]. The most detailed, detailed and generally accepted is the definition of the founder of this approach D. Marsh, who in 1994. first used the term "content and language integrated learning" (whose acronym "CLIL" is currently used in the scientific and methodological literature in different languages). Later, this concept became the official name of the subject-language integrated approach. D. Marsh and then D. Coyle give a more detailed explanation of this concept, defining it as an educational approach in which disciplines or their individual sections are taught in a foreign language, thus, a dual goal is pursued: studying the content of the discipline and simultaneously learning a foreign language [8].

D. Coyle, to characterize the essence of CLIL, developed the 4"C" scheme, which is presented in the form of a triangular pyramid with four vertices:

1. "content"
2. "communication"
3. "cognition"
4. "culture"

Each component of the design proposed by D. Coyle has indicators.

"Content" is designed to answer the questions: "What are the goals of learning?", "What to teach?", "What new learners learn?", "What is the result of this training?"

"Communication" defines the working language of teaching, the creation of a special dictionary, language correction in the learning process, the choice of types of communication, while pointing out the need to use debatable forms of interaction in the educational process.

"Cognition" highlights the mental skills that determine the concentration of attention on the subject and the language being studied, the types of questions leading to the correct answers, the tasks necessary for reasoning.

"Culture" involves the choice of the socio-cultural meaning of the topic and the integration of all the material of the lesson, and also involves taking into account the individual qualities of students.

The main methodological principles of CLIL were determined by K.S. Grigorieva[2]:

1. Multiculturalism;
2. Sustainable learning;
3. Development of thinking skills of a higher order;
4. Intensive and productive knowledge of the teacher in a foreign language;
5. A variety of methodological techniques;
6. Use of authentic teaching material.

According to the classification of F. Ball, who notes in one of his works the relatively recent emergence of a domain-language integrated approach (CLIL), as well as the difficulty of recognizing this approach in practice, two versions of the implementation of a domain-language integrated approach are distinguished: based on learning content (content-driven) and based on language learning (language-driven)[5]. Also in foreign scientific and methodological literature, such concepts as "hard" and "soft" CLIL are often found.

When implementing the "soft" (soft) version of CLIL, the educational process focuses on a foreign language, its study becomes one of the main tasks. This model assumes that teachers of language subjects present the material through some scientific or professional context.

Based on the analysis of the specific features of the "soft" version of the subject-language integrated approach, the following stages of introducing this CLIL model into the process of teaching a foreign language were identified:

1. Review and selection of the necessary educational and methodological material;
2. Distribution of means and techniques of pedagogical communication;
3. Direct implementation of CLIL in the learning process.

Based on the principles of a subject-language integrated approach, the following pedagogical conditions are required at the first stage of implementation[1]:

1. Correct definition of the object of study;
2. Correct selection of material, taking into account the psychological aspects of cognitive activity;
3. Obligatory consideration of age characteristics.

Thus, at the first stage, the teacher needs to analyze and select the necessary educational and methodological material corresponding to the level of knowledge of a foreign language, in particular English, and the profile subject of students.

This standard, which is necessary for the successful conduct of foreign language classes within the

framework of a subject-language integrated approach, must also follow the 4 "C" scheme [8]:

1. The content of the educational material is aimed at improving the skills and abilities in the core subject;
2. Communication defines the communicative goal of discussing the topic of a specialized subject through a foreign language;
3. Knowledge focuses on the combination of acquired knowledge with the expression of one's own thoughts in a foreign language;
4. Culture involves the selection of material aimed at understanding and defining oneself, the people around and the world as a whole. The use of a subject-language integrated approach requires a thorough, time-consuming preparation from the teacher.

Moreover, this process dictates the need for constant creative search. However, as mentioned earlier, this approach does not require an increase in academic hours for mastering a foreign language and a decrease in the hourly load on specialized subjects.

Thus, when planning and conducting a lesson using CLIL, a certain algorithm of actions is observed at the initial stage: the material is analyzed and selected, means of pedagogical communications are planned for further practical application. Choosing a version of CLIL or varying it (soft-hard) can become an extremely effective learning model at all stages of introducing this approach into the educational process.

I would also like to note about the basic principles of CLIL.

CLIL principles

- CLIL is, first of all, teaching general knowledge, not multilingualism, so the latter is only an additional feature;
- Training is based on the main 4 "C": content, communication, cognition and culture. All these components are in continuous connection with each other;
- Requires building a safe psychological climate in the classroom;
- Implies the use of only one (foreign) language, the same teacher and audience;
- for a better understanding of the material, the teacher can use facial expressions, gestures, pictures, presentation sound, etc.

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